

CHARACTERIZATION OF DISEASES RELATED TO ENVIRONMENTAL FACTORS AT THE POPULATION LEVEL AND FEATURES OF EARLY PREVENTION

Mamasolieva N.S.

Tojiboeva L.R.

Usmonov B.U.

Andijan State Medical Institute

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The purpose of the study was to study the epidemiological description of certain diseases related to ecofactors in the valley conditions and to determine the features of early prevention.

Research materials and methods. Screening was carried out in the adolescent population of the valley (1500) and epidemiological, biochemical, instrumental, clinical, functional and statistical methods were used. Screening for chronic diseases was analyzed and evaluated.

Results and conclusions. Most chronic kidney diseases (mainly pyelonephritis) are detected in the adolescent population. For example, complicated types are recorded with a frequency of 3.7 percent and uncomplicated types with a frequency of 96.3 percent ($R < 0.0001$). The main reason for this was the high frequency of prelithiasis and urolithiasis in the examined patients.

In the ecological conditions of the valley, the risk of an unfavorable epidemiological situation (increasing the risk of complications of diseases) for teenagers was confirmed to be born mainly from 12 different diseases. They are noted in those examined with the following frequencies: enterocolitis - 14.3%, prostatitis - 3.6%, intestinal ulcer disease - 1.2%, stomach ulcer disease - 1.5%, anemia - 26.4%, neurocirculatory asthenia - 11.6 percent, goiter - 7.4 percent, urolithiasis - 3.7 percent, chronic cystitis - 7.4 percent, chronic duodenitis - 2.9 percent, chronic gastritis - 2.8 percent and arterial hypertension - 18.5 percent.

Therefore, we think that these results will be appropriate to be taken into account in the implementation of programs for early detection and elimination of environmental diseases starting from adolescents in the ecological conditions of the valley, or they will be important in reducing medical losses.

